

IMPACT OF INTERNET USAGE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: BOTH POSITIVE & NEGATIVE

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Abstract

Millions of individuals use the internet as a platform for the creation and exchange of information. Indeed, this fact has a significant and profound impact on both social life and academic success. In the evolution of information technology, the internet is a fundamental technology. The knowledge-based society now considers the Internet to be an essential tool. The way things are done is changing as a result of the usage of technology. This includes the work done in universities where the teaching and learning process is changing. It is crucial to understand how technology affects student achievement. This study looked into how using the internet affects academic performance. Both the institution and the students may benefit from this paper. Institutions can spend more on online resources to improve their students' academic performance and yield better outcomes. Additionally, it will give readers a thorough understanding of the numerous internet resources and how students can use them to raise their academic performance.

Keywords: Internet, academic achievement and students

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INTRODUCTION: The Internet is made up of a network of millions of computers that are connected to one another on a global scale; it is a medium that does not place a limit on the amount of information that can be accessed by a user. Because the Internet has so many benefits

and can make a lot of tasks easier, it is beneficial for effectiveness and efficiency. The effectiveness and efficiency of a specific Internet, like the Internet, may be seen in the way that it offers its users a wide range of services that make life easier and more enjoyable. The growth of information and communication technology is being facilitated by the existence of the internet. One outcome of the sophistication and development of science and artificial technology is the Internet. The term "internet" is an acronym for "interconnected networking," which in Indonesian denotes a collection of linked computers across various networks. The Internet offers many benefits to everyone on a daily basis, but students particularly benefit from it. Additionally, the Internet, which is a relatively new source of scientific resources and is filled with a wealth of knowledge, varies greatly in terms of its objectives, target audiences, dependability, and other factors. Therefore, it's critical that end users are educated on the standards by which information content should be evaluated and are aware of the wide range of information that is available on the Internet. The definition of the Internet is that it is the greatest computer network in the world that connects all computers, connected devices (such as smartphones and tablets), switches, routers, hubs, and other connecting devices, as well as the computer itself, into a single container. Between 1996 and 2001, there was a significant increase in the amount of time spent using e-mail and surfing the web; different Internet usage patterns have been linked to both positive and negative outcomes; dysphoric symptoms have been linked to a variety of internet activities, including shopping, playing games, and research; the study's findings suggest that Internet use is one of the primary factors influencing students' academic performance and social lives. In Ghana, 60% of people agreed that education in 2020 would be considerably different from how it is today. To make the most of technological resources, teleconferencing and distance learning will be widely used. Additionally, many learning activities will move to being personalised and just-in-time. "Hybrid" classes, which combine elements of online learning with the absence of on-campus lectures, will also be widely used.

Over the past decade, the Internet has become an integral part of life for the majority of the population. Of course, the Internet is of great importance in the modern world and brings great benefits to humanity: as an inexhaustible source of information, a tool for organizing the educational process, as an indispensable assistant in work and business, as a means of conducting and planning leisure time and much more. Today, any modern person at least once a day, for communication, work or simply searching for the necessary information, visits the World Wide Web and part of the population of our planet no longer represent their lives without

the Internet. However, excessive addiction to the Internet negatively affects the psyche and emotional sphere of a person. The enormous rise in Internet usage in recent years has had unfavourable psychiatric repercussions, including Internet addiction and, in some cases, a condition that is akin to a mental disorder. Long-term active efforts have been made in Asian nations to curb overuse of the Internet. The issue with utilising the Internet, which has spread to every country in the world today, can be broadly characterised as the inability to control one's online behaviour, which has detrimental effects on day-to-day activities. According to quantitative research (Sampath Kumar & Manjunath, 2013), teachers and academics have been using the internet to support their research and instruction. Their academic performance has improved as a result of using the internet, specifically since writing research papers helps students conduct better research and learn more effectively. Additionally, (Sushma et al., 2014) found that a student's Internet addiction increased with the amount of time they spent on it. The study demonstrated that internet usage is increasingly used as a gauge of academic success. Beyond the allotted period, using the Internet won't be a sign of academic success.

Internet Usage's Effects on Student's Academic Achievement

The tedious days of having to visit the library and leaf through a tonne of dusty books in order to locate the necessary information are long gone. The internet is a global network of

interconnected systems that enables intuitive distant communication. The internet was initially sent in 1969, but it wasn't until the 1990s that it became accessible to the broader public. The study found that, especially among young people, the internet has become a widely used resource for sexual wellbeing information. Although there are undeniable benefits to the

internet, there are also numerous and growingly detrimental effects. People are using the internet in the wrong ways.

Positive Impacts of Internet Usage on Academic Achievement

The best way to obtain information about anything is via the internet, which simplifies our work. It offers the most efficient forms of communication, including email and instant chat. Online banking and shopping have made life less confusing. With the availability of countless

books and journals online, training has significantly improved. Exploration has been easier as a result. Online course admissions are simple for students. The internet is a must-have for pupils in today's classrooms because it offers so many benefits to them. Below, we list each benefit or good thing that the internet has done for kids' education.

- a. **Internet connectivity and communication:** Additionally, the Internet facilitates interaction and communication between professors and students. Students and teachers can connect with one another and communicate with one another via the internet. Many students and teachers benefit from the ability to easily discuss educational resources with one another online via the internet.
- b. **Online learning using the Internet:** Many tasks, including schooling, are made simpler for individuals by the Internet. Prior to the internet, it was exceedingly challenging for students to obtain information from the appropriate sources and from the appropriate individuals. They invest a lot of money and valuable time in their education, as well as waste both. However, with the internet, it has become more simpler for the pupils. They don't need to squander their valuable time by going to class. Students can simply learn at

home using the internet. They do not need to travel so far from their home to the study. It is simple to obtain at home.

- c. **Assistance with completing projects and presentations:** Students can also use the internet to do their homework and tasks. They make it simple for students to finish their assignments and presentations. I personally used the internet to gather information for my assignments and presentations. The internet truly broadens my learning for me, which is a big assistance. The internet helps us learn more and more things, and in better ways.
- d. **Internet practise is available to students:** The finest forum for students to practise their professions is the Internet. The internet is the finest practise environment for students interested in learning various computer-related languages who work in the IT or computer science fields. On the internet, there are numerous websites that they can use to practise and learn more.
- e. **Internet-based content that is relevant:** prior to the internet's creation. In order to find the pertinent information for their studies, students used to read a variety of books. They found it quite challenging to research information in the large books, which wastes a lot of pupils' valuable time. However, with the internet, it has become more simpler for pupils. On the internet, they can find their study materials with ease. There is a wealth of information and knowledge on the internet. On the internet, you may find the best and most relevant stuff. Students can use the internet to look for all of their available online assignments, quizzes, presentations, and other study-related items.

Negative Impacts of Internet Usage on Academic Achievement

In addition to its benefits and beneficial outcomes, the internet also has a negative impact on students. The internet has several negative effects on a student's academic performance. Internet use is more likely to distract kids from their studies and divert them to other types of activity.

- a. **Communication Skills of Students Drop:** Since the internet greatly eases students' lives and offers many benefits to students, Although it enhances communication, it also has a significant impact on pupils' communication abilities. Students can readily locate the material they're looking for online because the internet is regarded as a veritable gold mine of knowledge and information. They avoid social interaction outside because of this. Students use the internet to engage in online browsing. The students were shackled to it. The majority of students use the internet for pleasure instead of going outdoors to engage

in other activities and socialise with others. The children' communication skills and talents gradually deteriorate as a result. They are reliant on the web.

- b. **Increase the amount of time you spend online surfing:** The pupils' valuable time is one of the most significant things. For them, every second counts. However, they frequently waste their valuable time on the internet. Due to internet usage, students frequently lose concentration on their academics and learning and become involved in other kinds of activities, such as playing games and watching movies.
- c. **Use of the Internet too much:** The addiction to excessive internet use is one of the worst negative consequences of the internet on kids' academic performance. The introduction of the internet has an impact on the majority of students. Student education, study, and learning are significantly disrupted as a result of internet addiction. All of the negative effects of the internet are mostly caused by internet addiction. The root cause of all the negative impacts of the internet is internet addiction. The most hazardous impact of the internet on students' academic performance is online addiction.
- d. **Destruction from the Study:** The Internet is the most distracting thing in a student's educational life. Most students are addicted to the internet and use the internet all the time for surfing, playing video games, watching movies, and videos, listening to music, and many more. They get distracted from studying and learning. Most of the students get

distracted in their study and learning time. Due to the internet, they cannot focus on their study and learning.

Conclusion: For students, the Internet is a tremendously effective tool for education and learning. It is a rather modern creation. The benefits and drawbacks of the internet for pupils in the classroom come first. The pupils' use of the Internet will determine whether it is used for good or bad. Despite how useful the internet is for students, it may also be damaging to them. It is our obligation to watch over how our kids and pupils utilise the internet for research and education. This paper's conclusion is that internet use is one of the elements that affects academic achievement. Unless the internet is used for learning and academic objectives, the amount of time spent online will have an impact on the students' social lives. This essay demonstrates the direct correlation between academic success and Internet use for research purposes.

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